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O.Konashevych THE USE OF BLOCKCHAIN IN MICROGRIDS12

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..... $N = pq, \quad p \quad q$,17

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A
{ $A_{[1]}, A_{[2]}, \dots, A_{[n]}$ } [5],

(
 A
 $B = A_{[1]}$ [2].

B
{ $B_{[1]}, B_{[2]}, \dots, B_{[m]}$ } , $B_{[1]} = A_{[1,1]}$,
⋯

$B_{[2]} = A_{[1,2]}$ $B_{[m]} = A_{[1,m]}$.
 B
{ $B_{[1]}, B_{[2]}, \dots, B_{[m]}$ } .

$A_{[a]}, A_{[b]}, A_{[a,b]}$ A .

:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{[a]} \cdot A_{[b]} &= A, \\ A_{[a]} \cdot A_{[a,b]} &= A_{[a]}, \\ A_{[b]} \cdot A_{[a,b]} &= A. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$A_{[a]} \cdot A_{[b]} = A \quad A_{[a,b]} \cdot A_{[b,a]} = A ,$$

$$A_I \cdot A = A \quad A \cdot A_I = A , \tag{2}$$

I _ () .

A

$$+ \quad A_{[a]}, A_{[b]}, A_{[a,b]} \quad A$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_{[a]} + A &= A_{[a]}, \\ A_{[a]} + A_{[b]} &= A_{[a]} + A_{[b]}, \\ A_{[a]} + A_{[a,b]} &= A_{[a,b]}, \\ A_{[b]} + A_{[a,b]} &= A_{[b]} + A_{[a,b]}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

(3)

$$\begin{aligned} A_{[a]} + A &= A_{[a]} & A_{[a]} + A_{[a,b]} &= A_{[a,b]} & A_{[a]} + A_{[b]} &= A_{[a]} + A_{[b]} \\ A_{[b]} + A_{[a,b]} &= A_{[b]} + A_{[a,b]} \end{aligned} \quad [3]$$

(2)

[4].

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Intel® C++

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[1]:

LARD (locality aware request distribution) -

CAP (client aware policy) -

[2];

[3].

(SaaS, PaaS).

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620.9, 681.32.

O.Konashevych, PhD student of Pukhov Institute for Modelling in Energy Engineering, City of Kyiv

THE USE OF BLOCKCHAIN IN MICROGRIDS

Two innovative ideas of microgrids [1] and blockchain [2] has a great potential of use together. Microgrids conception was first proposed by R. Lasseter, and developed in systematic view by Jeremy Rifkin in his conception of the The Third Industrial Revolution [3].

Conventional power stations, such as coal-fired, gas and nuclear powered plants, as well as hydroelectric dams and large-scale solar power stations, are centralized and often require electricity to be transmitted over long distances. By contrast, distributed energy resources systems are decentralized, modular and more flexible technologies, that are located close to the load they serve, albeit having capacities of only 10 megawatts (MW) or less [4].

Distributed energy resources systems typically use renewable energy sources, including small hydro, biomass, biogas, solar power, wind power, and geothermal power, and increasingly play an important role for the electric power distribution system. A grid-connected device for electricity storage can also be classified as a distributed energy resources system, and is often called a distributed energy storage system. By means of an interface, distributed systems can be managed and coordinated within a smart grid [4].

Microgrids are modern, localized, small-scale grids, contrary to the traditional, centralized electricity grid (macrogrid). Microgrids can disconnect from the centralized grid and operate autonomously, strengthen grid resilience and help mitigate grid disturbances. They are typically installed by the community they serve. Microgrids increasingly employ a mixture of different distributed energy resources, such as solar hybrid power systems, which reduce the amount of emitted carbon significantly.

As such microgrids are not so widely spread among the world there is lack of experience of using them and which is more important there are no standard solutions for managing of such grid.

The issue of energy balance and accounting systems are open issues. The main problem that along with idea of distributed power generation we still see the centralized approaches of managing. But managing grid where large amount of consumers at the same time are producers is a rather challenging issue.

The idea of smart contracts [5] based on blockchain platform is a hypothetical answer.

The distributed interaction by using special software in a Peer-To-Peer computer network was practically and successfully implemented in Bitcoin cryptocurrency [6]. Bitcoin network operates without central administration, and even without any kind of administration, without, middleman or any kind of moderators providing virtual currency turnover among people.

Certain scope of human and machine interaction was algorithmized as a computer code which is performed by user's computer in the network without any central managing with so-called principal as "distributed consensus".

Distributed consensus is the mathematical model of social rules. The rules are performed not by people but by computers.

The idea to use blockchain in microgrids has common genesis of the distributed society. By reducing central authority it is proposed to perform peer-to-peer interaction using self-governed social structures based on such smart networks where interaction provided by set of computer rules.

What gives blockchain in smartgrid:

- distributed accounting of produced and consumed power, such information is online and publicly stored:

- possibility to make smart-contracts (self executed contracts) to buy and sell power within the microgrid;

- providing smart balance.

Smart balance is the idea where issues of providing power balance are solved by programed rules performed within the computer network of power producers and consumers.. Each consumer produce and consumes energy and compensate the lack of power by purchasing it from central energy producer or micro producers. The basis of such balance lies between planning of power consumption and free market price. So each consumer plan his demand in power and consumes by paying planed price and overpays by consuming unplanned amount of power. By producing and storing power, consumer satisfies his own demand in power or sells it for profitable price.

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[2]. () .

[2], « « » (: algorithm) (« »)

(: logarithm),

Webster's New World

Dictionary, 1957 —

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[2] , : - « « »

«algorithm»

[3] ».

(: input)

(: output)

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1. . . . / . . . // . — , 1973. — 164 .
2. . . . 1. / . . . // 3— « » . — , 2000. — 720 .
3. : / . . . // . — 2—e . — : « » , 2005. — 1290 .
4. . — , 1986. — 367 . / . . // « » , 2—e . — : « » , 2005. — 1290 // . —

511.13 : 003.26.

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$$N = pq,$$

$$p \cdot q,$$

RSA

(Rivest, Shamir, Adleman)

[2].

... (

$$N = p \cdot q$$

[3]

$$N = p \cdot q, \quad p \cdot q, \quad [1],$$

$$(B \in \mathbb{N}).$$

10^6

22

$x \bmod B$.

c

$$(B),$$

B

$$B = b1 \cdot b2$$

$$b1 \cdot b2.$$

1.

$$n = pq, \quad p \cdot q,$$

2. Song Y. Yan. Cryptanalytic attacks on RSA / Song Y. Yan – Springer Science and Business Media, Inc. 2008. – .255

004.942

[2,3], [1] (1)

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = \varphi x(t) - a_0 x^2(t). \quad (1)$$

(2)

$$(1 + a_1 x(t)) \frac{dx(t)}{dt} = \varphi x(t) - a_0 x^2(t), \quad (2)$$

x -

; φ -

; a_1, a_0 -

[4]

(1) (2)

« - » [5],

[6]

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.1 (-)

1

		a_1	φ	a_0
()		$-2,578 \cdot 10^{-5}$ $\pm 2,874 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ $\pm 1,96 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$5,88 \cdot 10^{-7}$ $\pm 4,582 \cdot 10^{-6}$
		-----	2,505 $\pm 19,008$	$6,42 \cdot 10^{-5}$ $\pm 4,334 \cdot 10^{-4}$

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2. / : - , 2012. - 128 .
3. / , - : - , 1993. - 302 .
4. : / -2- - : - , 2009. - 228 .
5. , / , - : - , 2004. - 464 .
6. , - : - , 1966. - 724 . /

688. 321

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RSA

GNFS [1]
 kGNFS

MPI OpenGL.

$n = 2n_1 + 1$ RSA- , $n_1 -$
 $p = 2k_1 + 1, q = 2l_1 + 1$.

$$(2k_1 + 1)(2l_1 + 1) = 2n_1 + 1, \tag{1}$$

$$2k_1l_1 + k_1 + l_1 = n_1. \tag{2}$$

$$k_i, l_i \geq 0. \quad \text{mod } 2 \quad 2k_1l_1 + k_1 + l_1 \equiv n_1 \pmod{2} .$$

$$p = 2P + 1 = 2k_1 + 1, \quad q = 2Q + 1 = 2l_1 + 1, \quad p, q$$

$$k_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \quad l_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \quad k_1 + l_1 \equiv 0, \quad P, Q .$$

H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n ,

688. 321

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(Gs)
 $\varnothing, f_i > f_j,$
 $n_i < n_j, n_i - \varnothing.$
 (Gp)

$Gs \quad Gp$

$$Wh(s_i) = (n_i - 1)(N)^{n-1} + \sum_{i_2=1}^N P(a_2 = s_{i_2}) Wh(s_{i_2} | a_1 = s_i) \quad (1)$$

$$Wh(T) = \sum_{i=1}^n n_j N^{n-j} \quad Gp,$$

$Gs,$

[1], X

Y.

$Gp.$

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2. -2013.- 1.- .154-161. //

3. -1999.- 1.- .30-35 . //

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» [3].

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004.94

∴ ∴ , , , , - -

[1] :

$$y(t) = \int_0^t K_1(t-s)x(s)ds + \int_0^t \int_0^t K_2(t-s_1, t-s_2)x(s_1)x(s_2)ds_1ds_2 + \dots, \quad (1)$$

$x(t)$, (t) - , t - , $K_i(t-s_1, \dots, t-s_i)$ - .

$y(t)$. $x(t)$, $x(t)$, (,) [2].

(1) :

$$x(t_i) = \frac{y(t_i) - \frac{hK_1(t_i, t_0)x(t_0)}{2} - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} hK_1(t_i, t_j)x(t_j) - \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} \sum_{g=0}^{i-1} h^2 K_2(t_i, t_j, t_g)x(t_j)x(t_g)}{\frac{1}{2}hK_1(t_i, t_i)},$$

$$i = \overline{1..n}, \quad h = t_i - t_{i-1}, \quad x(t_0) = \frac{y'_i(t_0)}{K(t_0, t_0)}$$

$$(1) \quad t, \quad K(t_0, t_0) \neq 0.$$

1. . . , / . . . — 2014. — 10. — 59-67.

2. . . // . . . — 2012. — 1. — 60-68.

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Daphnia magna S.

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TLC

TLC (TLA

Checker)

(Amazon Web Services) [1].

Amazon

TLC- (BFS, Breadth-first Search) Depth-first Search).

(DFS,

: CPU – AMD K10, 3GHz; RAM – DDR3, 2 GB, dual channel; OS – MS Windows 7x32; JRE – 1.7 (. 1).

. 1.

. 1 n - , t -

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BIG DATA

... , ...

online. (

« V», : (Volume), (Variety), (Velocity), (Variability), , Big Data

Big Data, (CI) CI Big Data. CI, online-

(online).

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() () .

$$mX = mA \omega^2 \cos \beta \sin \omega t - mg \sin \alpha + F, \quad (1)$$

m - ; ω - ; α - ; -
 ; β - ; F -
 F () .
 N
 f (F = Nf) .

$$X = -g \frac{\sin a - \text{arctg}(f)}{\cos(\text{arctg}(f))} + A \omega^2 \frac{\cos(\beta + \text{arctg}(f))}{\cos(\text{arctg}(f))} \sin \omega t, (2)$$

arctg(f) -

(1) (2)

f -

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$$B = c \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \frac{\rho v^2}{2}, \tag{3}$$

$$m_0 = 0,67 \pi \rho r^3, \tag{4}$$

$$mX = - m_0(X-); \tag{5}$$

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3. // : .- : - . . . ,2005. - 11.- .250-253.

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(Maranzana algorithm), « Drop algorithm », (Teitz-Bart algorithm Bump-and-Shift algorithm), GRIA (Global-Regional Interchange Approach,).

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